

NEW NORMAL-BASED INSTRUCTIONAL MATERIALS AND GRADE 7 STUDENTS PERFORMANCE IN TLE-ELECTRONICS

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study was to evaluate the new normal-based instructional materials as a new delivery mode of instruction in this time of pandemic and its contribution on the improvement of students' performance in TLE of Grade 7 students. This is a descriptive correlational research which aimed to determine the effectiveness of instructional materials among the 150 electronics students at Col. Lauro D. Dizon Memorial Integrated High School. The self-made questionnaire was used in this study and validated by experts in the field of TLE electronics. The responses from the respondents were administered through questionnaire. The result was analyzed using mean, standard deviation and Pearson Product-Moment Coefficient (Pearson-r). The study revealed that the respondents were mostly 11 to 13 years of age. There were more male respondents. Most of the respondents have fathers that were employed and mothers that are unemployed. Most of the respondents have fathers and mothers who are college graduates. Most of the respondent's parents' monthly income range is Php 5,000 - 10,000. The result shows that majority of the students have good level of performance with a grade of 75 in both test result and practice task. The results indicate that the majority of the respondents performed well. There is no significant relationship between the components and characteristics/qualities of the instructional materials in electronics and students' performance in both test result and practice task on the instructional materials. The hypothesis stating that the perception of the respondents on the components and characteristics/qualities of the instructional materials in electronics in terms of learning outcomes, content, activities, assessment and their performance is not significantly related to test result and practice task is sustained. The assessment tool, on the other hand, indicates no significant relationship in terms of test result hence the hypothesis in this respect is not sustained.

Keywords: instructional materials, component, characteristics/characteristics, test result, practice task